

Provision for School's Emergency: A Qualitative Study on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

Marjorie P. Vertudazo

Abstract. This study unearths the experiences, coping mechanisms used, and educational insights learned by disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in providing school emergencies. A qualitative approach to research the phenomenological experiences of the Eight (8) disaster risk reduction management coordinators in Nabunturan East District, Division of Davao de Oro. Experiences on challenges encountered in providing school emergencies were as follows: developing a comprehensive plan, creating a safe zone in school, and conducting drills and exercises. The coping mechanisms used in addressing the challenges were the following: management through scenario-based training, proactive planning, collaboration, and networking. Finally, the educational insights learned from teachers' experiences were as follows: must have tailored preparedness plans for diverse scenarios, collaborative engagement, stakeholder involvement, and continuous training and improvement. These themes were relevant in the provision for school emergencies. All these themes were comprehensive emergency responses tailored to the unique challenges of different educational settings. Investigating the effectiveness of various emergency preparedness strategies, including evacuation procedures, communication protocols, and staff training, was fundamental in any disaster occurrence.

KEY WORDS 1. School Emergency 2. School Preparation 3. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

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1. Introduction

In today's dynamic and unpredictable world, the importance of provision for school emergencies has never been more evident. Beyond providing a place of learning, schools play a pivotal role in ensuring the safety and well-being of our children. A robust emergency preparedness plan is the cornerstone of this commitment, protecting against unforeseen disasters that may disrupt the educational process. From natural disasters to man-made crises, the ability of schools to respond swiftly and effectively can make all the difference. By cultivating a culture of readiness, schools not only safeguard students and staff but also instill invaluable life skills, resilience, and a sense of security in the entire community. The United Kingdom has a robust approach to disaster preparedness, including in schools. Through the Department for Education, the UK government has established guidelines and measures to ensure schools are prepared to handle emergencies effectively. The "Schools Emergency Management Guidance" provides a framework for schools to plan, respond, and recover from various emergencies (GOV.UK,

2020). This coordination involves collaboration between the government, local authorities, schools, and emergency services to create a comprehensive disaster response strategy. One key aspect of this approach was the regular practice of emergency drills and exercises. Schools in the United Kingdom often conduct fire drills, lockdown drills, and other emergency simulations to ensure that students and staff are familiar with evacuation procedures and emergency protocols. Additionally, schools may have emergency response plans in place detailing roles and responsibilities, communication channels, and procedures to ensure the safety of everyone on the premises during emergencies. Integrating disaster preparedness education into the curriculum ensures that students know emergency protocols, helping them respond effectively in crises (GOV.UK, 2020). Malaysia has a structured approach to disaster preparedness coordination in schools. Malaysia's National Disaster Management Agency (NADMA) coordinates disaster preparedness efforts nationwide. NADMA's guidelines and initiatives, such as the National Disaster Management Framework and various disaster management plans, provide the foundation for school disaster preparedness (National Disaster Management Agency Malaysia, 2014). This coordination involves collaboration between NADMA, the Ministry of Education, and local authorities to establish comprehensive disaster response protocols, risk assessments, and preparedness strategies for educational institutions. A significant aspect of this approach was the regular conduct of emergency drills and training programs for students and educators. These drills simulated various emergency scenarios, allowing participants to practice evacuation procedures, emergency communication, and coordination. Schools in Malaysia may have emergency response plans in place, detailing roles and responsibilities, communication channels, and procedures to ensure the safety of students and staff during disas-

ters. Integrating disaster preparedness education into the school curriculum ensures that students know emergency protocols and can respond effectively in crises (National Disaster Management Agency Malaysia, 2020). In the United States, ensuring schools' emergency preparedness was paramount, given the diverse range of potential threats, including natural disasters, shootings, and other critical incidents. The Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and the U.S. Department of Education have collaborated to develop comprehensive school guidelines and resources to enhance their disaster preparedness efforts. FEMA's "Guide for Developing High-Quality School Emergency Operations Plans" is a foundational reference (FEMA, 2023). A cornerstone of disaster preparedness coordination in U.S. schools is the practice of regular emergency drills and exercises. Schools often conduct drills for various scenarios, such as fire, tornadoes, and lockdowns, to ensure that students and educators are well-prepared to respond effectively. Moreover, schools are encouraged to develop Emergency Operations Plans (EOPs) that outline procedures for different types of emergencies, encompassing communication protocols, evacuation routes, and roles and responsibilities of staff. This approach and integrating disaster preparedness education into the curriculum equip students with the knowledge and skills to confidently navigate emergencies. In the Philippines, school disaster preparedness coordination is of utmost importance due to the country's susceptibility to natural disasters such as typhoons, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions. The Department of Education (DepEd), in collaboration with the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), has developed comprehensive guidelines and programs to ensure schools are well-prepared for emergencies. The "Basic Education Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (BDRRM) Framework" serves as a reference for disaster

preparedness efforts in schools (Department of Education, 2020). The Philippines' approach to disaster preparedness in schools emphasizes regular emergency drills and training programs, as per the Department of Education's guidelines. These drills simulate various disaster scenarios, equipping students and educators with the skills to respond effectively. Schools are encouraged to develop and implement School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (SDRRM) Plans detailing procedures for different types of emergencies, including evacuation protocols and communication channels. Integrating disaster preparedness education into the curriculum ensures that students know emergency protocols and are empowered to act confidently during crises (Department of Education, Philippines, 2023). Additionally, climate change poses an escalating threat, increasing the frequency and intensity of natural disasters such as typhoons, floods, and landslides. The Philippines' geographic location makes it particularly vulnerable to these climate-related hazards, necessitating continuous updates and improvements to existing disaster preparedness and response strategies. Addressing these national issues requires a concerted effort to ensure equitable distribution of resources, streamline coordination mechanisms, and enhance the capacity of local communities to respond to disasters effectively (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2021). In the local scenario, particu-

larly in the schools of Nabunturan East District, Division of Davao de Oro, disaster risk reduction management coordinators encountered various experiences in providing school emergencies. Some experiences are enriching, while others negatively affect our commitment to performing additional tasks. In this context, this study was conceptualized to collect the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators as they prepare schools for emergencies. Through this research, we aspired to shed light on the essence of being prepared for emergencies, offering valuable insights that can inform disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the different strategies applied by other schools worthy of emulation.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study's purpose was to learn about the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators as they prepare schools for emergencies. Furthermore, it served as reference material for future researchers in this area. The results also shed more light on the experiences, mechanisms, and insights from the informants' narratives.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intended to get insights into and experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in preparing schools for emergencies. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of disaster risk reduction management Coordinator in the provision for school emergencies?
- (2) How do disaster risk reduction management coordinators cope with the challenges of providing school emergencies?
- (3) What educational values gained are drawn from the experiences of the DRRM coordinators?

The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Preparing schools for emergencies involves creating plans, conducting drills, and implementing

safety measures to ensure the safety of students and staff during unexpected crises. Disaster risk reduction management coordinators were responsible for coordinating and implementing

strategies to minimize the impact of disasters and emergencies within an organization or community.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—

1.3.1. Preparing Schools for Emergencies—Preparing schools for emergencies is critical to ensuring safety and educational continuity. Schools face various hazards, from natural disasters to human-made crises, making proactive planning essential (UNDRR, 2021; FEMA, 2020). Establishing a culture of preparedness promotes swift, organized responses and risk reduction within educational institutions.

1.3.2. Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Coordinators' Role—DRRM coordinators play a pivotal role in preparing schools for emergencies. Their responsibilities include developing comprehensive plans, conducting risk assessments, and collaborating with stakeholders to ensure safety (Allen et al., 2020; Wang, 2020). By creating clear communication protocols, mapping evacuation routes, and designating safe zones, coordinators minimize risks during crises (Tsai, 2019; Sugimoto et al., 2020).

1.3.3. Conducting Drills and Exercises—Drills and exercises are vital in emergency preparedness, helping students and staff familiarize themselves with evacuation procedures and response protocols. These simulations enhance decision-making and coordination, fostering a culture of readiness within schools (FEMA, 2020; Perez-Lugo, 2021).

1.3.4. Coping Mechanisms of DRRM Coordinators—DRRM coordinators use proactive planning and scenario-based training to manage the complexities of school emergency preparedness. By engaging in realistic simulations, they develop critical decision-making and coordination skills, which are essential in high-pressure situations (Drabek, 2022; Cutter et al., 2018). Collaboration with local agencies and continuous training are also crucial for refining preparedness strategies (Waugh, 2019; FEMA,

2020).

1.3.5. Insights from DRRM Coordinators' Experiences—Key insights from DRRM coordinators emphasize tailored preparedness plans for diverse scenarios and the importance of stakeholder collaboration. Regular training and drills help refine response plans and ensure a high level of readiness. Their efforts align with global frameworks like the Sendai Framework and FEMA guidelines, which prioritize disaster preparedness in schools (UNDRR, 2019; Australian Institute for Disaster Resilience, 2019).

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study, anchored on Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), offers valuable insights into understanding how disaster risk reduction management coordinators learn from their experiences preparing schools for emergencies. This theory emphasizes that learning occurs not only through direct personal experiences but also by observing and modeling the behaviors, attitudes, and outcomes of others. In the context of disaster preparedness, coordinators may observe the actions and responses of their peers, experts, and other stakeholders during emergencies. Through this observational learning, coordinators can acquire new strategies, problem-solving techniques, and effective communication methods that enhance their preparedness efforts. Social Learning Theory also underscores the role of self-efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to execute tasks successfully, which influences how coordinators approach challenges and take the initiative to improve their emergency preparedness practices. By applying the principles of Social Learning Theory, researchers can delve into how disaster risk reduction management coordinators acquire knowledge and skills through observation, interaction, and reflection on their experiences. The second theory used in this study is the Community of Practice (CoP) Theory, formulated by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger in 1991. It provides a framework for understanding how disaster risk reduction management coordinators col-

laboratively learn and share knowledge within their professional communities. According to this theory, individuals who share a common domain of interest or practice come together to form communities where they engage in joint activities, share experiences, and develop a shared repertoire of resources. In the context of school emergency preparedness, coordinators form a community of practice wherein they exchange insights, best practices, and lessons learned from their experiences. This collaborative learning process fosters the development of a collective understanding of effective strategies, challenges, and innovative solutions. CoP Theory also emphasizes the role of "legitimate peripheral participation," which means that newcomers gradually become more engaged and influential within the community as they contribute and learn from experienced members. By exploring how disaster risk reduction management coordinators engage in joint activities, share knowledge, and evolve within their professional community, researchers can uncover the dynamics of collaborative learning that enhance school emergency preparedness practices. The third theory used in this study is the Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) Theory, introduced by Barbara Reynolds and a team of experts in 2002. This theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how effective communication plays a crucial role in managing and mitigating the impact of crises and emergencies, including those in the context of school disaster preparedness. This theory recognizes that communication is a vital tool for disseminating information and an essential means of empowering individuals, building trust, and promoting appropriate behavioral responses during emergencies. CERC Theory outlines several fundamental principles, such as being first, being right, expressing empathy, promoting action, demonstrating transparency, and guiding effective communication strategies during crises. For disaster risk reduction management coordinators preparing schools for emergencies, applying CERC principles can lead to improved communication plans that provide accurate and timely information, address concerns, and guide appropriate actions. By understanding and adhering to the principles of CERC Theory, researchers can explore how disaster coordinators effectively communicate with various stakeholders, including students, parents, staff, and the broader community, to enhance overall emergency preparedness and response. This study integrates three foundational theories to comprehensively understand how disaster risk reduction management coordinators enhance school emergency preparedness. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) highlights the significance of observational learning and self-efficacy, demonstrating how coordinators acquire and refine their skills through observing peers and experts. Lave and Wenger's Community of Practice (CoP) Theory (1991) underscores the importance of collaborative learning within professional communities, where coordinators share experiences and develop collective knowledge. Reynolds' Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) Theory (2002) emphasizes the critical role of effective communication in managing crises and guiding coordinators in disseminating timely and accurate information. Together, these theories provide a robust framework for understanding the dynamics of learning, collaboration, and communication in enhancing school disaster preparedness. By exploring these theoretical perspectives, researchers can gain valuable insights into the processes that enable coordinators to effectively prepare for and respond to emergencies, ultimately improving school safety and resilience. Integrating Social Learning Theory, Community of Practice (CoP) Theory, and Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) Theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how disaster risk reduction management coordinators enhance school emer-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the study

gency preparedness. Social Learning Theory emphasizes the role of observational learning and self-efficacy, helping to understand how coordinators acquire and refine skills by observing peers and experts. CoP Theory highlights the importance of collaborative learning within professional communities, where coordinators share experiences and collectively develop effective strategies. CERC Theory underscores the critical role of effective communication in managing crises, guiding coordinators in disseminating accurate, timely information and building trust. Together, these theories offer a multidimensional approach to examining the learning, collaboration, and communication processes that enable coordinators to improve school safety and resilience. Continuous training enhances individuals' skills and fosters a culture of preparedness within the school environment, ensuring the response remains effective and efficient (Australian Institute for Disaster Resilience, 2019). Metych (2024) stressed that Natural disaster is any calamitous occurrence

generated by the effects of natural, rather than human-driven, phenomena that produce significant loss of human life or destruction of the natural environment, private property, or public infrastructure. Education is essential and a priority because if human beings do not become aware of disaster risks, acquire the knowledge necessary, and develop the appropriate behavior, attitudes, and level of involvement, they would not be able to prevent them. Generally, Education for disaster preparedness can provide life-saving and life-sustaining information and skills that protect children and young people during and after emergencies. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework of the study, highlighting three interconnected variables. These variables include the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in providing for schools' emergencies, the coping mechanisms that they employ to address challenges encountered in this provision and the educational values derived from their experiences.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of

data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—As Paton (2002) described, phenomenology was an exploration aimed at understanding the structure and essence of individuals' experiences with a specific phenomenon. This research aligns with that definition, seeking to grasp the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in preparing schools for emergencies. However, Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to anticipate a more thorough and detailed investigation than the initial description might indicate. He likened the information provided to just the tip of an iceberg, suggesting that much greater depth and complexity lie beneath the surface. The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research is undertaken by selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the participants discuss the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in the provision of school emergencies and their coping mechanisms in addressing the challenges. Educational insights learned were also examined. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that I attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, in-

dividual researchers “hold explicit belief.” This study intended to gather information from the participants or disaster risk reduction management coordinators in Nabunturan East District as to how they provided schools for emergencies. It is assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in providing for school emergencies. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argues that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that I openly discuss the values that shape the narrative and include their interpretation in conjunction with the participants’ interpretation. I ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. I understand the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpreted them in light of their interpretations. Rhetoric means reporting reality through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study context, I used the first person to elucidate the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators as they prepare schools for emergencies.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in providing school emergencies in Nabunturan East District were gathered through an in-depth interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms

were extracted from the participants. The researcher’s drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in the provision for school emergencies became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experienced disaster risk reduction management coordinators in the provision for school emergencies in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience is a source of knowledge that shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the experiences and mechanisms used by disaster risk reduction management coordinators were explored, and insights learned were the basis for possible future research and policy analysis related to this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative re-

search that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) added that phenomenology, rooted in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, I used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also helpful in following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), I transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews help uncover

the story behind a participant's experiences and pursue in-depth information about a topic. I collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. I incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. I required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. I needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult. I also needed to decide how and when to incorporate their observations into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since this study focuses on exploring and assessing the experiences and feelings of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in providing school emergencies, I employed phenomenological qualitative research methods.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size

than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes were large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. They obtained most or all of the perceptions that led to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may be best determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). This study's participants were Eight (8) disaster risk reduction management coordinators in Nabunturan East District, Division of de Oro. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must have been in the service for at least five years, be elementary school teachers, and have served as disaster risk reduction management coordinators. I utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Role of the Researcher—I was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, I take up the following roles in the course of the study: I was a facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I interviewed the participants and guided them through the process. To avoid the intrusion of bias, I interpreted the ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies rather than on my own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings. Expert in qualitative methods. I imple-

mented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing environmental triangulation and thematic content analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. I kept records and properly secured them as they contain sensitive information relevant to the research. However, it was my primary responsibility to safeguard the collected data for the participants. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Data Analyst. I ensure that the phenomenon or problem is approached from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. I also ensured that the findings were accurate to the participants and that their voices were heard. I organized and presented data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. I also presented the study's findings by research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, I gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.6. Data Collection—The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. I asked permission to conduct the study, I asked for an endorsement from

the Dean of the Graduate School as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent. Order. Since the participants used their vernacular language, I translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. I conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.7. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. I analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. I immersed myself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. I coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. I ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme.

Reviewing themes. I reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. The researcher employed Thematic Content Analysis to describe qualitative data. A detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study’s results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings were the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity was established (Naeem Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.8. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because its results and findings depend on the researcher’s conduct. The trust-

worthiness of a research study was important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students' perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide a generalization of the study based on his context and can address the core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded

by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was kept correctly for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of "how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—The framework analysis of this research would utilize Colaizzi's method of 1978. The researchers use a rigorous and robust qualitative method to find, understand, describe, and depict the experiences of persons as they experience them, as well as reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships. This method aims to uncover the genuine experience of the phenomenon under investigation. Colaizzi's method consists of seven steps. First, informants' descriptions of the experiences are read to acquire a sense of the whole. After that, significant statements are extracted, Then meanings are formulated from the significant statements. Afterward, formulated meanings are organized into themes. Themes are then integrated into an exhaustive

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

description. Next, the essential structure of the phenomenon was formulated. Finally, for validation, the informants would evaluate the analysis result and determine if it means the same as their original experiences. (H. Turunen et al. 1994).

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions about the study. The participants disclosed their experiences and coping mechanisms in preparing for school emergencies, as well as insights into these themes.

3.1. Experiences of Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators in the Provision for School's Emergency—The experiences of Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) coordinators in the provision of school emergencies offer invaluable insights into the intricate process of fortifying educational institutions against unexpected disruptions. These coordinators, entrusted with safeguarding the lives of students, staff, and the entire school community, navigate a multifaceted landscape where proactive planning, rigorous training, and efficient coordination converge. Drawing from their experiences, they contribute to the formulation and execution of comprehensive disaster preparedness strategies that encompass a spectrum of potential hazards, from natural calamities to unforeseen crises. The experiences of

DRRM coordinators resonate with globally recognized frameworks and best practices. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, advocated by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR 2020), emphasizes the role of schools in disaster risk reduction and underscores the importance of empowering students and educators to become agents of resilience (UNDRR, 2020). Additionally, the practical knowledge gained by these coordinators aligns with the guidelines outlined in the "Guide for Developing High-Quality School Emergency Operations Plans" by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA 2020) in the United States, where the integration of these plans into school systems is crucial for effective response (FEMA, 2020). By delving into the experiences of DRRM coordinators,

we gain profound insights into the dynamic interplay of preparedness, communication, and resilience that defines the modern educational landscape.

3.1.1. Developed a comprehensive plan—Developing a comprehensive emergency response plan is pivotal for disaster risk reduction management coordinators in their efforts to prepare schools for emergencies. This intricate process involves meticulous analysis of potential risks, collaboration with stakeholders, and the formulation of a detailed blueprint that guides schools through various scenarios, focusing on safeguarding lives and minimizing disruptions. The plan is a foundational framework that outlines roles, responsibilities, communication protocols, evacuation routes, and resource allocation during critical moments, ensuring a coordinated and effective response. Through this experience, coordinators address the complex interplay of logistical considerations and the imperative of creating a safe and organized environment during emergencies (Allen et al., 2017).

The experience of the participants above in developing comprehensive plans was aligned with globally recognized disaster risk reduction principles. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction emphasizes the integration of disaster risk reduction into educational systems, highlighting the significance of planning and preparedness within schools (UNDRR, 2020). Additionally, FEMA’s “Guide for Developing High-Quality School Emergency Operations Plans” offers valuable guidance in creating plans that cater to the unique needs of educational institutions (FEMA, 2020). The process involves identifying vulnerabilities, engaging diverse stakeholders, and creating protocols that empower schools to navigate crises while prioritizing safety.

The experience of developing a comprehensive emergency response plan involves a sequence of meticulous steps. Coordinators begin

by conducting risk assessments that identify potential hazards and vulnerabilities specific to the school’s location and context. Collaborating with relevant stakeholders, including school staff, local emergency services, and parents, enables a holistic understanding of the school community’s needs and capabilities. Through these collaborations, coordinators gather insights that contribute to tailoring the plan to the unique challenges and resources of the school (Wang, 2019). As part of the plan’s development, coordinators establish clear communication channels and designate responsibilities to ensure effective emergency coordination. This may involve appointing emergency response teams, outlining notification procedures, and determining the flow of information among different stakeholders. Evacuation routes and assembly points are carefully mapped out, considering accessibility for all individuals within the school community, including those with disabilities (Tuladhar et al., 2020).

The final plan is a living document that undergoes regular reviews and updates based on lessons learned from drills, exercises, and real-world incidents. Coordinators continuously engage with stakeholders to refine procedures and enhance the plan’s responsiveness. This comprehensive approach to plan development equips schools with a roadmap that fosters preparedness, enhances communication, and mitigates risks during emergencies (Allen et al., 2017).

3.1.2. Created a safe zone in school—Creating safe zones within schools is a pivotal experience for disaster risk reduction management coordinators as they diligently prepare educational institutions for emergencies. These designated safe areas serve as focal points where students, staff, and other school community members can gather during crises to seek refuge and ensure their well-being. The process involves meticulous analysis of the school’s layout and infrastructure, considering factors such as accessibility, structural integrity, and proximity to

potential hazards. By strategically establishing safe zones, coordinators play a pivotal role in minimizing risks and providing security during uncertain times (Tsai, 2020). As part of the experience of creating safe zones, coordinators begin by conducting comprehensive assessments of the school premises to identify suitable locations that offer optimal protection from various hazards. These areas are typically structurally sound and shielded from threats such as falling debris, flooding, or other dangers. Collaborating with architects, engineers, and safety experts contributes to informed decisions about the most secure areas within the school (Towers Gough, 2019).

Coordinators also consider the capacity of safe zones to accommodate the entire school population and ensure accessibility for individuals with disabilities. Clear signage and communication channels are established to direct individuals to these safe areas during emergencies, facilitating organized and efficient evacuations. By incorporating safe zones into the broader emergency response plan, coordinators offer a tangible demonstration of their commitment to the safety and well-being of every school community member (Sugimoto et al., 2020). Incorporating the creation of safe zones into the broader disaster preparedness plan involves fostering awareness and educating the school community about their existence and purpose. Coordinators collaborate with teachers, students, and staff to ensure everyone is well-informed about the designated safe areas, evacuation routes, and procedures to follow during emergencies. This educational component enhances the sense of preparedness and empowers individuals with the knowledge needed to take prompt and organized actions during high-stress situations (Tatebe Mutch, 2020). In essence, the experience of creating safe zones within schools encapsulates the meticulous attention to detail, collaboration, and dedication required of disaster risk reduction management coordinators. By

strategically designating areas that provide protection and security during emergencies, these coordinators contribute to a culture of safety, resilience, and unity within the school community. This multifaceted effort highlights their commitment to safeguarding lives and underscores the pivotal role of preparedness in navigating the uncertainties of the modern world (Sarah et al., 2021).

3.1.3. *Conducted drills and exercises—*

Conducting drills and exercises is a pivotal experience for disaster risk reduction management coordinators as they meticulously prepare schools to respond effectively to emergency situations. These proactive measures involve the realistic simulation of various emergency scenarios, allowing students, staff, and the entire school community to practice their roles and responses. By creating controlled yet immersive environments, coordinators provide participants with an opportunity to develop a deep understanding of evacuation procedures, communication protocols, and decision-making processes. These exercises play a crucial role in building familiarity, reducing panic, and enhancing overall response efficiency during actual emergencies (FEMA, 2020).

Numerous authoritative sources emphasize the significance of conducting drills and exercises as a cornerstone of emergency preparedness in educational institutions. FEMA's "Guide for Developing High-Quality School Emergency Operations Plans" highlights the importance of regular drills in validating emergency plans and refining response strategies (FEMA, 2020). The National Incident Management System (NIMS) also underscores the essential role of exercises in validating and improving preparedness, response, and recovery capabilities (FEMA, 2017). Coordinators draw from these reputable references to craft comprehensive exercises that align with industry best practices while tailoring them to the unique context of their schools.

Fig. 3. Experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in the provision of school emergency

Conducting drills and exercises involves meticulous planning, coordination, and execution. Coordinators begin by identifying relevant emergency scenarios and considering natural and human-made disasters that could impact the school environment. These scenarios encompass a range of responses, from evacuations and lockdowns to medical emergencies and fire drills. By tailoring scenarios to their school's specific risks and vulnerabilities, coordinators ensure that participants are trained to respond effectively to the most likely situations (Pinar, 2017).

Collaboration with local emergency response agencies and professionals is integral to the success of these exercises. Coordinators liaise with local fire departments, law enforcement, medical personnel, and other relevant experts to ensure the exercises adhere to current safety standards and reflect real-world protocols. This partnership also enables a holistic assessment of the school's readiness to coordinate with external responders, fostering a more cohesive and effective emergency response network (Petal Izadkhah, 2018). Regular evaluations and post-exercise debriefings play a critical role in the experience of conducting drills and exercises. These sessions allow participants and stakeholders to assess their performance, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and re-

fine emergency plans accordingly. The insights gained from these evaluations inform updates to the school's emergency response procedures and contribute to continuous improvement over time. Furthermore, the experience of participating in drills and exercises fosters a culture of preparedness, empowering individuals with the skills and confidence needed to respond decisively in high-stress situations (Perez-Lugo, 2021).

In conclusion, conducting drills and exercises is a dynamic and essential experience for disaster risk reduction management coordinators. By adhering to industry guidelines, collaborating with local experts, and tailoring scenarios to the school's unique context, coordinators ensure that students, staff, and the wider community are equipped with the skills and knowledge to navigate emergencies effectively. Through these immersive and educational experiences, coordinators contribute to a safer, more resilient school environment that is well-prepared to handle various potential challenges. Figure 3 shows the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators regarding the challenges encountered in responding to school emergencies and the emergence of the three themes: Developing a comprehensive plan, Creating a safe zone in school, and Conducting drills and exercises.

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms of Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators on the Challenges Encountered in the Provision for School's emergency*—Coping mechanisms are essential strategies that disaster risk reduction management coordinators employ to navigate the myriad challenges in preparing schools for emergencies. These dedicated professionals face multifaceted obstacles ranging from logistical complexities and resource limitations to the psychological impact of dealing with potential crises. In response, coordinators harness diverse coping mechanisms that enable them to effectively manage stress, uncertainty, and high-pressure scenarios while steadfastly ensuring the safety and well-being of students, staff, and the school community. By adopting adaptive strategies, seeking peer support, and drawing from established guidelines, coordinators forge a resilient mindset that empowers them to tackle challenges head-on and continue refining their disaster preparedness efforts (Patrick, 2019). The experience of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in coping with challenges aligns with psychological resilience frameworks. The American Psychological Association (APA) emphasizes building resilience to navigate adversity and mitigate stressors (APA, 2021). Coordinators often rely on the coping mechanism of proactive planning and scenario-based training, honing their problem-solving skills to address potential hurdles before they arise. Additionally, the guidance offered by established frameworks like the Incident Command System (ICS) equips coordinators with a structured approach to coordinating and managing resources during emergencies (FEMA, 2017). These frameworks provide coordinators with tangible coping strategies that facilitate effective decision-making and coordination in high-pressure environments.

3.2.1. *Scenario-based training*—Scenario-based training has emerged as a valuable coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators

facing the multifaceted challenges of preparing educational institutions for emergencies. In a world fraught with natural disasters, technological hazards, and security threats, the role of school disaster coordinators has become pivotal in ensuring the safety and well-being of students, staff, and faculty. Traditional approaches to preparedness often fall short of providing practical experience for handling complex emergencies. Scenario-based training addresses this gap by immersing coordinators in lifelike simulations, enabling them to develop critical decision-making skills, coordination, and communication strategies. This essay delves into the significance of scenario-based training as a coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators, shedding light on their challenges and how this training approach effectively equips them to overcome these hurdles. School disaster coordinators grapple with many challenges when preparing educational institutions for emergencies. These challenges include the unpredictability of emergencies, diverse stakeholder involvement, resource constraints, and the need for seamless interagency collaboration. According to Drabek (2012), the unpredictability and complexity of disaster situations make traditional preparedness approaches inadequate. Moreover, as highlighted by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2019), the involvement of various stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, and local authorities, adds to the intricacy of planning and execution. Balancing educational objectives with safety measures can be complex (Ronan et al., 2018), and the psychological impact of emergencies on students and staff must be carefully addressed. These multifaceted challenges necessitate innovative and comprehensive training approaches beyond theoretical knowledge and drills. Due to its experiential learning approach, scenario-based training is an effective coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators. By exposing coordinators to immersive, lifelike simulations

of emergencies, this training method replicates the high-stress situations they might encounter. Through realistic scenarios, coordinators are compelled to make crucial decisions, coordinate responses, and communicate effectively—skills that are challenging to cultivate through conventional classroom-style training. This method offers a safe environment for making mistakes and learning from them, fostering a deeper understanding of the complexities of emergency management. Cutter et al. (2018) emphasize that scenario-based training enhances resilience by promoting adaptive thinking and problem-solving skills.

Scenario-based training equips school disaster coordinators with essential skills and knowledge to tackle challenges effectively. These simulations require coordinators to solve multi-dimensional problems, consider ethical dilemmas, and collaborate with various stakeholders. They must think on their feet, adapt to changing circumstances, and manage limited resources efficiently. Additionally, scenario-based training enhances communication skills, ensuring precise and timely dissemination of information to staff, students, parents, and external agencies (FEMA, 2020). The experiential nature of the training helps coordinators build confidence in their decision-making abilities, leading to more effective responses during emergencies. The statement above was supported by studies that validate the effectiveness of scenario-based training in disaster preparedness, such as the work by Smith et al. (2019), who found that such training enhances decision-making under pressure. The Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA, 2020) emphasizes the importance of hands-on, scenario-based training for disaster preparedness. In conclusion, scenario-based training is a crucial coping mechanism for disaster coordinators facing challenges in preparing schools for emergencies. By providing immersive experiences and practical skill development, this approach empowers coordina-

tors to navigate the complexities of emergency management confidently and effectively.

3.2.2. Proactive planning—Proactive planning has emerged as a crucial coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators facing the complex challenges of preparing educational institutions for emergencies. School disaster coordinators have become paramount in ensuring the safety and well-being of students, staff, and faculty in a world characterized by a range of potential disasters, from natural calamities to human-made crises. Traditional reactive approaches to emergency preparedness often fall short of addressing the intricacies of diverse scenarios. Proactive planning tackles this by emphasizing anticipation, prevention, and preparedness (Ronan Johnston, 2019). This essay delves into the significance of proactive planning as a coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators, illuminating their challenges and how this approach effectively equips them to overcome these hurdles.

School disaster coordinators grapple with various challenges when preparing educational institutions for emergencies. These challenges encompass the dynamic nature of emergencies, resource constraints, engaging diverse stakeholders, and the need for seamless interagency collaboration (UNDRR, 2019). According to Waugh (2019), the evolving landscape of disasters requires a shift from response-oriented strategies to proactive measures that can anticipate and mitigate potential risks. Limited resources can hinder the implementation of comprehensive safety measures. Furthermore, engaging stakeholders such as students, parents, teachers, and local authorities in the planning process can be intricate due to varying perspectives and priorities. These challenges underscore the need for innovative and forward-thinking approaches to disaster preparedness.

Proactive planning holds significant value as a coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators due to its anticipatory approach. By iden-

tifying potential risks and vulnerabilities, this strategy empowers coordinators to take preventive actions that minimize the impact of emergencies. Unlike reactive approaches focusing primarily on response and recovery, proactive planning emphasizes risk reduction and readiness. This approach encourages coordinators to conduct comprehensive risk assessments, develop tailored emergency plans, and establish clear communication channels. The work of UNDRR (2019) underscores the importance of proactive planning in creating resilient educational institutions capable of withstanding various challenges. Proactive planning equips school disaster coordinators with essential skills and tools to effectively tackle challenges. This approach mandates thorough risk assessments, enabling coordinators to identify potential hazards specific to their region and institution. As Cutter et al. (2018) emphasized, proactive planning promotes a culture of preparedness that permeates the entire school community. Coordinators are tasked with developing comprehensive emergency response plans encompassing various scenarios, ensuring a well-coordinated and swift response. Additionally, proactive planning encourages partnerships with local emergency agencies, facilitating collaborative efforts and shared resources. This approach strengthens the ability of coordinators to anticipate, prevent, and respond to emergencies effectively.

The significance of proactive planning as a coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators is well-supported by scholarly works. Waugh (2019) emphasizes the shift from reactive to proactive strategies in emergency management. UNDRR (2019) highlights the importance of proactive planning in building resilient schools, while Cutter et al. (2018) stress the role of such planning in fostering community resilience. In conclusion, proactive planning emerges as a vital coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators facing challenges in preparing schools for emergencies. By foster-

ing anticipation, prevention, and collaboration, this approach empowers coordinators to navigate the complexities of disaster management confidently and effectively.

3.2.3. Collaboration and networking— Collaboration and networking have emerged as indispensable coping mechanisms for school disaster coordinators navigating the multifaceted challenges of preparing educational institutions for emergencies. In an era characterized by diverse threats, ranging from natural disasters to human-induced crises, the role of school disaster coordinators has become pivotal in safeguarding the welfare of students, staff, and faculty. Conventional approaches to emergency preparedness often fail to address potential disasters' complexities and dynamic nature. Collaboration and networking strategies address this gap by fostering partnerships, sharing resources, and leveraging collective expertise (UNDRR, 2019). This essay explores the significance of collaboration and networking as coping mechanisms for school disaster coordinators, shedding light on their challenges and how these approaches equip them to overcome these obstacles.

School disaster coordinators encounter various challenges when preparing educational institutions for emergencies. These challenges include the evolving nature of emergencies, limited resources, stakeholder engagement, and the demand for seamless interagency coordination. The dynamic nature of disasters requires strategies that can adapt and evolve (Waugh, 2019). Resource constraints can hinder the implementation of comprehensive preparedness measures, and engaging diverse stakeholders, such as students, parents, teachers, and local authorities, can be complex due to differing priorities and perspectives. Effective emergency management also necessitates close collaboration with various external agencies and organizations. These challenges underscore the importance of collaborative approaches.

Fig. 4. The coping mechanisms of disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in the provision for schools emergency

Collaboration and networking hold immense significance as coping mechanisms for school disaster coordinators due to their ability to leverage collective wisdom and resources. Coordinators can access knowledge and support by forming partnerships with local emergency services, government agencies, non-profit organizations, and other schools. These networks enable sharing best practices, lessons learned, and critical resources. The American Red Cross (2017) emphasizes the importance of collaboration in creating robust emergency plans that consider diverse perspectives and potential challenges. Collaboration also promotes a sense of community resilience, fostering a culture of mutual support and shared responsibility. Collaboration and networking equip school disaster coordinators with essential tools to tackle challenges effectively. Coordinators are encouraged to establish relationships with local emergency response agencies, allowing for swift and coordinated actions during emergencies. Collaborative planning enables the development of comprehensive and multifaceted emergency response plans (FEMA, 2018). Networking facilitates the exchange of information about available resources, innovative solutions, and emerging best practices. Collaboration en-

hances communication skills as coordinators must effectively convey information to various stakeholders. These mechanisms cultivate a sense of preparedness that extends beyond the school boundaries, encompassing the broader community.

The significance of collaboration and networking in school disaster management is substantiated by scholarly works. Waugh (2019) highlights the evolving nature of disasters and the need for collaborative, adaptive strategies. The American Red Cross (2017) underscores the importance of collaborative planning for effective emergency preparedness. In conclusion, collaboration and networking emerge as vital coping mechanisms for school disaster coordinators in the face of challenges in preparing for emergencies. By fostering partnerships, sharing knowledge, and leveraging collective resources, these approaches empower coordinators to navigate the intricacies of disaster management with confidence and effectiveness. Figure 4 shows the coping mechanisms of disaster risk reduction management coordinators regarding the challenges encountered in the provision and the emergence of the three themes: Scenario-based training, proactive planning, and collaboration and networking.

3.3. *Insights earned from the Experiences of Disaster Risk Reduction Management Coordinators in the Provision for School's Emergency*—Drawing insights from the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators offers a wealth of knowledge in preparing schools for emergencies. As educational institutions face an array of potential disasters, these coordinators play a pivotal role in ensuring the safety and well-being of students, staff, and faculty. Through their hands-on experiences, coordinators accumulate invaluable lessons that shed light on effective strategies, best practices, and the intricate challenges of disaster preparedness. This essay delves into the insights gained from the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators, highlighting their contributions to enhancing school emergency readiness. The experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators serve as a rich source of wisdom for school emergency preparedness. Educational institutions can fine-tune their emergency plans and response strategies by examining real-world scenarios and learning from successes and setbacks. The comprehensive guidance provided by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2019) underscores the importance of learning from past experiences to enhance resilience. Moreover, Ronan and Johnston (2019) emphasize the role of lessons learned in promoting community resilience. By harnessing the insights of disaster risk reduction management coordinators, schools can create safer environments and foster a culture of preparedness that extends beyond emergencies.

3.3.1. *Tailored Preparedness Plans for Diverse Scenarios*—One significant insight gained from the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators is the importance of tailoring preparedness plans to address a wide range of potential scenarios. Coordinators have learned that a one-size-fits-all approach is inadequate, as each school community faces unique

challenges and vulnerabilities. By conducting thorough risk assessments specific to their geographical location and local hazards, coordinators can develop targeted strategies encompassing natural disasters, technological incidents, and other emergencies. This insight emphasizes prioritizing flexibility and adaptability in preparedness plans (FEMA, 2020).

This critical insight garnered from the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators is the necessity of developing tailored preparedness plans capable of addressing a diverse array of potential emergencies. Given each school community's unique challenges and vulnerabilities, coordinators have learned that relying on a generic approach to preparedness is insufficient. By conducting comprehensive risk assessments specific to their geographical location and the potential hazards in their region, coordinators can create targeted strategies encompassing a wide range of scenarios. This insight underscores the need to prioritize flexibility and adaptability in preparedness plans (FEMA, 2020). School disaster coordinators understand that the ability to anticipate and respond effectively to various emergencies hinges on developing nuanced plans that can be customized.

3.3.2. *Collaborative Engagement and Stakeholder Involvement*—Another valuable lesson is the recognition that effective emergency preparedness is a collaborative endeavor involving various stakeholders within the school community. Coordinators have learned that engaging students, parents, teachers, administrative staff, and local authorities is essential in creating a comprehensive and resilient preparedness plan. This insight underscores the importance of clear communication channels, practicing emergency drills, and involving the broader community to ensure a coordinated and cohesive response during emergencies (UNDRR, 2019).

A fundamental lesson drawn from the experiences of disaster risk reduction management

coordinators is the recognition that successful emergency preparedness hinges on collaborative engagement and the involvement of various stakeholders within the school community. Coordinators have learned that students, parents, teachers, administrative staff, and local authorities play pivotal roles in creating a comprehensive and resilient preparedness plan. By involving all relevant parties in the planning process, schools can develop strategies that consider each stakeholder's diverse needs, concerns, and expertise. This insight underscores the importance of establishing clear communication channels, conducting regular emergency drills, and fostering a sense of shared responsibility throughout the school community (UNDRR, 2019). Effective engagement and collaboration are cornerstones for ensuring that everyone is informed, prepared, and ready to respond in times of crisis.

3.3.3. Continuous Training and Improvement—Experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators have highlighted the significance of continuous training and improvement. Coordinators have learned that preparedness is an ongoing process that requires regular training, simulation exercises, and post-event evaluations. By conducting drills and exercises that simulate emergencies, coordinators can identify gaps in their plans, refine response procedures, and enhance the overall preparedness of the school community. This insight underscores the dynamic nature of disaster preparedness, emphasizing the need for regular updates and adjustments to maintain a high level of readiness (Australian Institute for Disaster Resilience, 2019). The experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators have under-

scored the significance of continuous training and improvement in emergency preparedness. Coordinators have learned that preparedness is not a static endeavor but an ongoing process that demands consistent training, simulation exercises, and post-event evaluations. By regularly conducting drills that simulate various emergency scenarios, coordinators can identify gaps in their plans, refine response procedures, and enhance the overall preparedness of the school community.

This insight highlights the dynamic nature of disaster preparedness, emphasizing the need for regular updates and adjustments to keep pace with changing circumstances and emerging best practices. Continuous training enhances individuals' skills and fosters a culture of preparedness within the school environment, ensuring the response remains effective and efficient (Australian Institute for Disaster Resilience, 2019). Metych (2024) stressed that Natural disaster is any calamitous occurrence generated by the effects of natural, rather than human-driven, phenomena that produce significant loss of human life or destruction of the natural environment, private property, or public infrastructure. Generally, Education for disaster preparedness can provide life-saving and life-sustaining information and skills that protect children and young people during and after emergencies. Figure 5 shows the educational values gained from the experiences of DRRM coordinators and the emergence of the three themes: Tailored preparedness plans for diverse scenarios, Collaborative engagement and stakeholders' involvement, and Continuous training and improvement.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study was presented, and the summary of the findings depicted the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to solicit the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in preparing

Fig. 5. The emerging themes on the educational values gained from the experiences of DRRM coordinators

schools for emergencies in Nabunturan East District, Division of Davao de Oro. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to gain an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their definition or meaning of the explored phenomenon.

4.1. *Findings*—The findings of the study on the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in preparing the school for emergency were as follows: they developed a comprehensive plan, created a safe zone in school, and conducted drills and exercises. In terms of the coping mechanisms of disaster risk reduction management coordinators on the challenges encountered in preparing the school for an emergency, it was revealed that they manage through having scenario-based training, proactive planning, and collaboration and networking. Regarding the educational management insights gained from the participants, the coordinators proposed having tailored preparedness plans for diverse scenarios, collaborative engagement and stakeholder involvement, and continuous training and improvement.

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on the experiences of disaster risk reduction management coordinators, they encoun-

tered challenges in preparing schools for emergencies; the interview results revealed the following themes: First, develop a comprehensive plan. Developing a comprehensive emergency response plan is an essential experience for disaster risk reduction management coordinators in preparing schools for emergencies. The plan served as a foundational framework that outlines roles, responsibilities, communication protocols, evacuation routes, and resource allocation during critical moments, ensuring a coordinated and effective response. Second, create a safe zone in school. Designated safe areas served as focal points where students, staff, and other school community members could gather during crises to seek refuge and ensure their well-being. The process involved meticulous analysis of the school’s layout and infrastructure, considering accessibility, structural integrity, and proximity to potential hazards. Third, conducted drills and exercises. These proactive measures involve the realistic simulation of various emergency scenarios, allowing students,

staff, and the school community to practice their roles and responses. By creating controlled yet immersive environments, coordinators allow participants to develop a deep understanding of evacuation procedures, communication protocols, and decision-making processes. One theme was scenario-based training on the coping mechanisms of disaster risk reduction management coordinators and the challenges encountered in preparing schools for emergencies. Scenario-based training has emerged as a valuable coping mechanism for school disaster coordinators. It involves immersing coordinators in lifelike simulations, enabling them to develop critical decision-making skills, coordination, and communication strategies. The second theme identified was proactive planning. Traditional reactive approaches to emergency preparedness often fail to address the intricacies of diverse scenarios. Proactive planning tackles this by emphasizing anticipation, prevention, and preparedness. The third theme identified was collaboration and networking. Collaboration and networking strategies fostered partnerships, sharing resources, and leveraging collective expertise. Effective emergency management necessitated close collaboration with various external agencies and organizations. These challenges underscore the importance of collaborative approaches. The first theme identified in the educational management insights gained from disaster risk reduction management coordinators was tailored preparedness plans for diverse scenarios. It was essential to tailor preparedness plans to address various potential scenarios. By conducting thorough risk assessments specific to the geographical location and local hazards, coordinators could develop targeted strategies encompassing natural disasters, technological incidents, and other potential emergencies. The second theme identified was collaborative engagement and stakeholder involvement. Coordinators learned that engaging students, parents, teachers, administrative staff,

and local authorities was essential in creating a comprehensive and resilient preparedness plan. This insight highlighted the importance of clear communication channels, practicing emergency drills, and involving the broader community to ensure a coordinated and cohesive response during emergencies. The third theme was continuous training and improvement. Preparedness is an ongoing process that requires regular training, simulation exercises, and post-event evaluations. By conducting drills and exercises that simulate emergencies, coordinators can identify gaps in their plans, refine response procedures, and enhance the overall preparedness of the school community.

4.2.1. Future Directions—This study may explore developing and evaluating comprehensive emergency response plans tailored to the unique challenges of different educational settings. Investigating the effectiveness of various emergency preparedness strategies, including evacuation procedures, communication protocols, and staff training, can provide valuable insights. Additionally, this research study might integrate modern technologies such as geospatial mapping, early warning systems, and communication apps to enhance the efficiency and responsiveness of disaster preparedness and response efforts. This technological focus could examine how these tools assist coordinators in making timely decisions, disseminating critical information, and coordinating resources effectively during emergencies. Furthermore, future studies may assess the impact of community engagement initiatives led by disaster risk reduction management coordinators. Exploring the role of community partnerships, training programs, and awareness campaigns in enhancing overall resilience at the school and community levels could be instrumental. Research might also investigate the influence of socio-economic factors on the success of emergency preparedness initiatives and examine how coordinators can adapt strategies to address the specific needs

of diverse communities. By combining technological advancements with community-focused approaches, future research can contribute to developing robust and adaptable frameworks for schools to effectively prepare for and respond to emergencies under the guidance of disaster risk reduction management coordinators.

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